

THE EFFECT OF AGED MATERIALS ON THE AUTOCLAVE CURE OF THICK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In order to control the quality of composites fabricated from prepreg, specifications are available for shelf life and out time for various material systems. Once the shelf life has been exceeded, the prepreg must either pass acceptance tests or be disposed of. The objective of this work is to determine the lifetime of prepregs by evaluating the effect of aging on the curing of thick composites. The investigation is carried out by applying numerical simulations of the curing process for graphite/epoxy AS4/3501-6 composite laminates of 3cm thickness. The results indicate that fairly uniform compaction can be achieved in 3cm laminates when using prepreg with up to 10% initial curing. However, large nonuniformity in fiber volume fraction occurs when using prepregs with initial curing of 20% and 30%. In addition, the incomplete compaction that occurs when using initially cured prepregs causes large temperature overshoot during cure despite the lower heat of reaction.

KEYWORDS: prepreg aging, cure simulation, thick composites

INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing composite parts from prepreg requires careful storage of the materials in order to produce laminates that meet desired performance specifications. Since prepreg materials contain resins that cure continuously, they are usually stored in a freezer to slow the curing reaction. Although industry practice and requirements vary, large rolls of prepreg may be thawed and refrozen many times as material is needed. Every time the material is thawed to room temperature, the state of cure will advance somewhat. Subsequently, age and out time of these materials may affect the quality of laminates produced.

In order to control the quality of composites fabricated from prepreg, specifications are available for shelf life and out time for various material systems. In production facilities, a careful history of the time out of the freezer is maintained for each roll of prepreg. Once the recommended shelf life or out time has been exceeded, the material can not be used unless acceptance criteria is met. Since requalification of these materials is not feasible, they must be disposed of if they do not pass the acceptance tests. Since disposal costs sometimes exceed material costs, this can become very expensive in situations where material is not used regularly. Therefore, composites manufacturers have tried to determine the usefulness of aged prepregs.

To identify the effects of aging, several studies have been published which describe the changes in physical properties of composites fabricated from advanced prepregs. These include methods to detect aging such as dielectric measurements, dynamic mechanical analysis and differential scanning calorimetry as well as the determination of the effects of aging on mechanical properties [1-5]. These studies have been conducted on a variety of material systems including graphite/epoxy, polyimides, and bismaleimide modified epoxy/graphite prepreg. In this paper, the discussion will be limited to graphite/epoxy composites.

Sanjana [6] studied the aging behavior of Hercules AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg under ambient and various other heat and humidity conditions. Prepreg tack was found to deteriorate before any other property. A prepreg is defined as tacky when its glass transition temperature is lower than the ambient temperature. The loss of tack makes it difficult to fabricate composite components with complicated shapes. However, Sanjana found that mechanical properties did not deteriorate until much after tack had been lost. Scola [7] found similar results from aging tests performed on AS4/3501-6. Mechanical tests on composites fabricated from prepreg aged under humid conditions indicated that the properties were unaffected by this conditioning. However, tackiness was found to increase in prepregs conditioned at higher humidity due to plasticization of the resin.

Prepreg tack is a relative term and is therefore difficult to measure. Several tests are available that can be used for semi-quantitative measures of tackiness. These include tests which measure the distance a metal ball can roll across the surface of a prepreg. Other tests measure the adherence of a prepreg to a metal surface. Probably the most common method of determining the flow properties of prepreg is a squeeze flow test, which is described in an ASTM standard [8]. This test measures the amount of resin squeezed from several layers of prepreg at the approximate processing temperature. The results of this test are usually used to compare lots of material and determine if the prepreg is acceptable for producing parts.

While prepreg tack is necessary to layup complex geometry parts, the flow properties of the prepreg will also affect the ability to achieve complete compaction during cure. As curing proceeds, compaction occurs such that the outer plies, adjacent to the bleeder, are compressed first. Eventually compaction occurs in the interior layers. However, in thick composites, gellation of the resin sometimes occurs before compaction of all of the layers can be achieved. This was demonstrated for thick graphite/epoxy laminates by Campbell et al. [9]. Composite laminates were cured using different consolidation pressures. Tang et al. [10] quantified these results by measuring ply thicknesses from photo micrographs. The results indicated that for 60 ply laminates, full compaction was only achieved in the outermost layers, and even the laminates cured at the highest pressure contained uncompacted plies near the tool surface.

The problem of temperature overshoot and incomplete compaction during the cure of thick composites was studied through numerical simulations by Hojjati and Hoa [11]. The simulations were based on the curing model developed by Loos and Springer [12] and the squeezed sponge model for one-dimensional consolidation proposed by Dave et al. [13]. Several common cure cycles were applied to AS4/3501-6 composites ranging in thickness from 2.5 cm to 30 cm. The prepreg was initially considered to be unreacted. Nevertheless, the results showed that the maximum thickness for which the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle could achieve complete compaction was 3.0 cm. Application of a cure cycle that has been recommended for thick composites resulted in reduced temperature overshoot, but did not improve the compaction behavior.

Twardowski et al. [14] addressed the effect of using somewhat advanced prepregs on the processing characteristics of thick composites. Poor correlation in temperatures predicted by simulation with experimental results prompted the consideration that some initial aging of the prepreg could have led to lower heat generation during the curing reaction. Therefore, heat transfer simulations were performed for 5 cm laminates with initial degree of cure varying up to 40%. Compaction behavior was not considered in these simulation. The results showed that the magnitude of temperature overshoot decreased with increasing initial degree of cure.

Studies on prepreg aging available in the literature have determined that little effect on the mechanical properties result in thin laminates produced from advanced prepregs. However, the effect of aging on compaction of thick composites has not been addressed. Therefore, the goal of this work is to examine the effects of initial prepreg aging on the curing behavior of thick graphite/epoxy composites. Curing simulations will be used to evaluate the variation in processing characteristics due to the advanced state of prepreg.

ANALYSIS

Consider a fiber preform that is fully saturated with viscous resin and subject to uniform compressive loading and varying temperature boundaries as shown in Fig. 1. The applied temperature will cause the resin viscosity to drop and resin flow to occur. As the matrix material is displaced, compaction of the laminate will occur in the thickness direction. When curing large composite structures, most of the heat and resin flow will occur in the z direction only. Therefore, only the one-dimensional case is treated here.

Fig. 1: Schematic of a composite laminate subject to a compaction pressure, p_a , and cure temperature, T_b

The heat transfer analysis used for the composite during curing was developed by Loos and Springer [12]. This model assumes heat transfer to occur due to conduction through the thickness of the laminate. Heat is also generated inside the laminate as curing proceeds. The one-dimensional heat balance for the laminate is given by

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{c_p} \dot{H} \quad (1)$$

where α_z and c_p are the thermal diffusivity and heat capacity of the composite and \dot{H} is the rate of heat generation.

The rate of heat generation is determined by

$$\dot{H} = V_m H_{Rm} \frac{\rho_m}{\rho} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where H_{Rm} is the heat of reaction of the resin, α is degree of cure, V_m is matrix volume fraction, ρ_m is resin density, and ρ is the composite density. An expression for the rate of change of degree of cure was developed for AS4/3501-6 prepreg [15] as given by

$$\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} (K_1 + K_2\alpha)(1-\alpha)(.47-\alpha) & \alpha \leq 0.3 \\ K_3(1-\alpha) & \alpha > 0.3 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where

$$K_i = A_i \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_i}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

for $i = 1$ to 3 and R is the universal gas constant. A viscosity relation was also proposed

$$\mu = \mu_\infty \exp\left(\frac{U}{RT} + \kappa\alpha\right) \quad (5)$$

where μ_∞ and κ are constants and U is the activation energy for viscosity.

The governing equation for one-dimensional compaction and one-dimensional resin flow is essentially the same as that proposed by Dave [13]

$$-\frac{\partial p_a}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{V_f}{S_z^f \mu} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K_z \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where p_a is the external pressure applied to the laminate, p is resin pressure, V_f is fiber volume fraction, and S_z^f and K_z represent the compressibility and permeability of the fiber preform, respectively.

The fiber compressibility relates the change in fiber volume fraction to the effective fiber stress as given by the relation

$$S_z^f = \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_z^{fe}} \quad (7)$$

where σ_z^{fe} is the effective stress carried by the fiber preform. Several empirical relations have been developed between fiber volume fraction and effective fiber stress based on experimental results. The following expression was used by Hojjati and Hoa [11]

$$V_f = \begin{cases} -6.915 \times 10^{-7} \sigma_z^{fe} + 0.53 & 0 \leq -\sigma_z^{fe} \leq 68.7 \text{ kPa} \\ 0.1094 \log_{10}(-\sigma_z^{fe}) + 0.0486 & 68.7 \leq -\sigma_z^{fe} \leq 1030 \text{ kPa} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, S_z^f will change nonlinearly during compaction. Permeability will also change during compaction. One common relation for permeability as a function of fiber volume fraction is the given by the Carman-Kozeny equation,

$$K_z = \frac{r_f^2}{4C_z} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (9)$$

where r_f is the fiber radius and C_z is the Kozeny constant [16].

The initial conditions for the cure simulation are given by

$$T = T_\infty, \quad z \in \{0, h\} \quad (10)$$

$$p = p_a, \quad z \in \{0, h\} \quad (11)$$

where T_∞ is the ambient temperature. The boundary conditions are specified as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = 0, \quad z = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$p = 0, \quad z = h \quad (13)$$

$$T = T_b, \quad z = [0, h] \quad (14)$$

where T_b is obtained from the applied cure cycle.

The above equations were solved numerically using a Crank-Nicholson finite difference scheme in which all calculations are based on the variables at their average value between the current and past time steps. Eqns 1 and 6 were solved simultaneously. Since S_z^f and K_z change during the cure, they must be updated continuously. Therefore, an iterative approach was used. Good accuracy and convergence was found using a time step of one second and position steps of 0.1 cm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aging that will occur due to exposure of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg to ambient conditions can be calculated from the cure kinetics relations described above. The out time specified by Hercules for this prepreg is 10 days, but much longer out times have been considered in aging studies [17]. Assuming room temperature to be 25°C, consider the case of 30 days at this temperature. Using the input parameters listed in Table 1, the extent of reaction that could result during the out time was calculated to be 0.06 after 10 days and 0.16 after 30 days. Note, however, that the cure kinetics parameters were measured at very high temperatures. Since they are based on empirical data fitting, it is not clear how reliable they are at room temperature.

Table 1: Input parameters for cure kinetics calculations

Exponential factor, A_1 (min^{-1})	2.101×10^9
Exponential factor, A_2 (min^{-1})	-2.014×10^9
Exponential factor, A_3 (min^{-1})	1.96×10^5
Activation energy, ΔE_1 (J mol^{-1})	8.07×10^4
Activation energy, ΔE_2 (J mol^{-1})	7.78×10^4
Activation energy, ΔE_3 (J mol^{-1})	5.66×10^4
Heat of reaction, H_{Rm} (J kg^{-1})	4.73×10^5

In [11], it was determined that 3 cm is the maximum laminate thickness that can be produced with complete consolidation using conventional cure cycles. The recommended cure cycle for this material system consists of a 70 minute dwell at 116°C and a 130 minute dwell at 177°C with temperature ramp rates of 2°C/min. Modified cure cycles are available for thick composites which were found to reduce temperature overshoot. However, these cure cycles do not have a significant effect on the compaction behavior.

To determine the effect of prepreg aging on the cure of thick composites, simulations were performed for laminates with initial thickness of 3 cm and initial degree of cure ranging from 0.01 to 0.3. The input properties used for the simulation model are listed in Table 2. The manufacturer's recommended cure cycle was used throughout. Fig. 2 shows the change in thickness during cure for four different initial conditions. The results indicate that the maximum thickness change is obtained using an initial degree of cure of 0.01. The final laminate thickness obtained with $\alpha_{init} = 0.1$ is only 1.3% greater than that obtained with uncured material. However, the final thickness achieved with $\alpha_{init} = 0.2$ and 0.3 is found to be 6.3% and 18% greater than that obtained with new material.

Table 2: Input properties for simulation

Resin density, ρ_m (kg m^{-3})	1.26×10^3
Specific heat of resin, c_{pm} ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	1.26×10^3
Thermal conductivity of resin, k_{zm} ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.167
Fiber density, ρ_f (kg m^{-3})	1.79×10^3
Specific heat of fiber, c_{pf} ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	7.12×10^2
Thermal conductivity of fiber, k_{zf} ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	26
Fiber radius, r_f (m)	3.5×10^{-6}
Kozeny constant, C_z	6
Initial fiber volume fraction, V_{fi}	0.53
Activation energy for viscosity, U (J mol^{-1})	9.08×10^4
Viscosity constant, μ_∞ (Pa s)	7.93×10^{-14}
Viscosity constant, κ	14.1

Fig. 2: Change in thickness during cure for laminates with initial aging

The nonuniformity of consolidation through the thickness of the laminate is shown in Fig. 3. As expected, uniform consolidation was achieved with $\alpha_{init} = 0.01$. The small difference in final thickness achieved with $\alpha_{init} = 0.1$ results in only small inhomogeneity in fiber volume fraction through the thickness. The fiber volume fraction distribution for the laminate cured with $\alpha_{init} = 0.2$ indicates a variation between 0.6 and 0.68 throughout the entire laminate while $\alpha_{init} = 0.3$ resulted in approximately one quarter of the laminate remaining unchanged from the initial fiber volume fraction. While incomplete consolidation will affect mechanical properties by reducing fiber volume fraction, part performance will be more significantly affected by the nonuniform compaction and subsequent nonuniform properties.

Fig. 3: Distribution of fiber volume fraction after cure of laminates with initial aging

The effect of initial prepreg aging on temperature overshoot is examined. Fig. 4 shows midplane temperatures during cure for the 3 cm laminates. Comparison of maximum temperature overshoot obtained during simulations with $\alpha_{init} = 0.3$ and $\alpha_{init} = 0.01$ indicates a 10°C higher result for the aged prepreg. This behavior contradicts the results found in Ref. 14, where heat transfer simulations showed reduced temperature overshoot in laminates produced from aged prepreps. The reason for this difference is that compaction was neglected in the simulations of Ref. 14. Although less heat is generated by the curing reaction with initially aged materials, the laminate is 4.3 mm thicker than the initially uncured materials at the time that the maximum overshoot occurs. Therefore, the low thermal conductivity of the composite appears to be more significant than the heat of reaction of the resin.

Fig. 4: Midplane temperatures during cure for laminates with different initial aging

CONCLUSIONS

Storage recommendations provided by the material manufacturer do not provide a direct indication of the limitations of aged materials. Therefore, a study was conducted in which simulations were performed for autoclave curing of composite laminates with various thicknesses and with materials of different conditions. A numerical code was implemented to solve the one-dimensional heat transfer as well as the resin flow and fiber deformation during cure. The results showed that fairly uniform compaction can be achieved in 3cm laminates when using prepreg with up to 10% initial curing. However, by applying a 30 day out time, it was shown that resins in prepreg can advance to 16% when kept at conditions of 25°C. When prepreps with initial curing of 20% and 30% were used, large nonuniformity in fiber volume fraction was found. Also, large temperature overshoot occurred during cure with partially cured prepreg due to the poor compaction. This shows that partially curing prepreg is not a viable approach to controlling temperature overshoot in thick composites.

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